

PREDICTION OF OPEN HOLE COMPRESSIVE FAILURE FOR QUASI-ISOTROPIC CFRP LAMINATES BY MMF/ATM METHOD

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1 Introduction

The accelerated testing methodology (ATM) [1] was proposed for the prediction of long-term fatigue strength of CFRP laminates based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP). Based on ATM, the long-term fatigue strength for CFRP laminates and structures can be predicted by measuring the short-term fatigue strengths at elevated temperatures. The applicability of ATM was confirmed for CFRP laminates and structures combined with PAN based carbon fibers and thermosetting resins [2-4]. Furthermore, the advanced accelerated testing methodology (ATM-2) was proposed in which the formulation for the master curves of time-temperature dependent fatigue strength was performed based on Christensen's theory [5] which describes statistically the crack kinetics in viscoelastic body.

The failure criteria of separated fiber and matrix in polymer composites have been developed and the failure of composite structures has been predicted based on the analyses on micromechanics, laminates and structure levels. Recently, the stress-based micromechanics of failure (MMF) have been proposed by Sung-Kyu Ha and others [6] for polymer composite with viscoelastic matrix.

In this paper, the procedure of MMF/ATM method combined with ATM-2 and MMF is proposed for the fatigue life prediction of the structures made of CFRP laminates. The validity of MMF/ATM method is confirmed through the following two steps. As the first step, the master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters of CFRP are determined by measuring the static and fatigue strengths at elevated temperatures in the longitudinal and transverse, tension and compression directions of unidirectional CFRP. As the second step, the open hole

compression (OHC) fatigue strengths of quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates as an example of CFRP structures are measured at elevated temperatures, and these experimental data are compared with the predicted results by using the master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters of CFRP based on MMF/ATM method.

2 ATM-2

ATM-2 is established with following three conditions: (A) the failure probability is independent of time, temperature and load history; (B) the time and temperature dependence of strength of CFRP is controlled by the viscoelasticity of matrix resin. Therefore, the TTSP for the viscoelasticity of matrix resin holds for the strength of CFRP; (C) the strength degradation of CFRP holds the linear cumulative damage law as the cumulative damage under cyclic loading.

The long-term fatigue strength exposed to the actual loading where the temperature and load change with time can be shown by the following equation based on the conditions (A), (B) and (C).

$$\begin{aligned} \log \sigma_f(t', T_0, N_f, R, P_f) = & \log \sigma_{f0}(t_0', T_0) \\ & + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - n_r \log \left[\frac{D^*(t', T_0)}{D_c(t_0', T_0)} \right] \\ & - \frac{(1-R)}{2} n_r \log(2N_f) + n_r^* \log(1 - k_D) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The first term of right part shows the reference strength (scale parameter for the static strength) at reduced reference time t_0' under the reference temperature T_0 .

The second term shows the scatter of static strength as the function of failure probability P_f based on condition (A). α is the shape parameter for the strength.

The third term shows the variation by the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin which depend on temperature and load histories. n_r is the material parameter. The viscoelastic compliance D^* in (1) can be shown by the following equation:

$$D^*(t', T_0) = \frac{\varepsilon(t', T_0)}{\sigma(t', T_0)} = \frac{\int_0^{t'} D_c(t' - \tau', T_0) \frac{d\sigma(\tau')}{d\tau'} d\tau'}{\sigma(t', T_0)} \quad (2)$$

$$t' = \int_0^t \frac{d\tau}{a_{T_0}(T(\tau))}$$

where D_c shows the creep compliance of matrix resin and $\sigma(\tau')$ shows the stress history. t' is the reduced time at T_0 , a_{T_0} shows the time-temperature shift factor of matrix resin and $T(\tau)$ shows the temperature history.

The fourth and fifth terms show the degradation by the cumulative damage under cyclic load. The N_f and R show the number of cycles to failure and the stress ratio at the final step, respectively. n_f and n_f^* are the material parameters. The k_D shows the accumulation index of damage defined as the following equation based on the condition (C).

$$k_D = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{n_i}{N_{fi}} < 1 \quad (3)$$

where n_i and N_{fi} are the number of cycles and the number of cycles to failure at the loading of step i , respectively.

3 Procedure of MMF/ATM method

The procedure of proposed MMF/ATM method is shown schematically in Figs. 1 and 2. Figure 1 shows the first step for the prediction procedure by MMF/ATM method that is the process of determination of MMF/ATM critical parameters.

First, the viscoelastic modulus in the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP is measured at various temperatures. The master curve and the time-temperature shift factor are determined by using these test data based on the TTSP. Second, the static and fatigue strengths in the typical four directions of unidirectional CFRP are measured at various temperatures at a single loading rate and single loading frequency, respectively. The strengths in four directions are the longitudinal tension X , the longitudinal compression X' , the transverse tension Y and the transverse compression Y' , respectively. Third, the master curves of these strengths are determined by using the measured data and the time-temperature shift factor for viscoelastic modulus. Fourth, the master curves of four MMF/ATM critical parameters, the fiber tensile strength T_f , the fiber compressive strength C_f , the matrix tensile strength T_m , and the matrix compressive strength C_m are determined through the method described in [7].

Figure 2 shows the second step for the prediction procedure by MMF/ATM method that is the life determination of CFRP structures. With the master curves of the MMF/ATM critical parameters, the long-term strength prediction of CFRP becomes possible. Three-step stress analyses are necessary to process the test result, including stress analysis for "homogenous" CFRP structures and CFRP laminates in macro level and stress analysis for the constituents in micro level by stress amplification. From the master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters and failure criteria for fiber and matrix, the strength of CFRP structure under arbitrary time to failure and temperature can be determined.

Fig. 1. First step for prediction procedure by MMF/ATM method: Determination of MMF/ATM critical parameters

Fig. 2. Second step for prediction procedure by MMF/ATM method: Life determination of CFRP structures

4 Experiments

The test specimens were fabricated from unidirectional CFRP and QIL [45/0/-45/90]_{2s} of T800S/3900-2B which consists T800S carbon fiber and epoxy resin 3900 with toughened interlayer. The unidirectional CFRP were used to back-calculate the constituent properties. The QIL was used for strength prediction verification. The dynamic viscoelastic tests were performed for various frequencies and temperatures for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP. The shift factors for constructing master curve hold for the strength master curves of CFRP and constituent critical parameters' master curves. The static and fatigue tests for four directions of unidirectional CFRP were carried out to extract constituent critical parameters' master curves by micromechanical amplification. The OHC tests for QIL under static and fatigue loadings were carried out at various

temperatures. The OHC static test specimen is 118mm in length, 38.1mm in width, 3mm in thickness with $\phi 6.35$ mm hole in the center. The OHC fatigue test specimen is 150mm in length, 43mm in width, 3mm in thickness with $\phi 6.35$ mm hole in the center. The OHC static and fatigue tests for QIL under various temperatures were carried out as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Specimen of OHC tests

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Creep compliance of matrix resin

The left side of Fig. 4 shows the loss tangent $\tan \delta$ for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP versus time t , where time t is the inverse of frequency. The right side shows the master curve of $\tan \delta$ which is constructed by shifting $\tan \delta$ at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t until they overlapped each other, for the reduced time t' at the reference temperature $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$. Since $\tan \delta$ at various constant temperatures can be superimposed so that a smooth curve is constructed, the TTSP is applicable for $\tan \delta$ for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP.

The left side of Fig. 5 shows the storage modulus E' for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP versus time t . The right side shows the master curve of E' which is constructed by shifting E' at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t with same shift amount for $\tan \delta$ and logarithmic scale of E' until they overlapped each other, for the reduced time t' at the reference temperature $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$. Since E' at various constant temperatures can be superimposed so that a smooth curve is constructed, the TTSP is applicable for E' for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP.

The time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ which is the horizontal shift amount shown in Fig. 6(a) can be formulated by the following equation:

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) H(T_g - T) + \left[\frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T_g} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) + \frac{\Delta H_2}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_g} \right) \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)) \quad (4)$$

where G is the gas constant, 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(K•mol)], ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 are the activation energies below and above the glass transition temperature T_g , respectively. H is the Heaviside step function. The temperature shift factor $b_{T_0}(T)$ which is the amount of vertical shift shown in Fig. 6(b) can be fit with the following equation:

$$\log b_{T_0}(T) = \left[\sum_{i=1}^5 b_{i-1} (T - T_0)^{i-1} \right] H(T_g - T) + \left[\sum_{i=1}^5 b_{i-1} (T_g - T_0)^{i-1} + \log \frac{T_g}{T} \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)) \quad (5)$$

where b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3 and b_4 are the fitting parameters. The creep compliance D_c of matrix resin was back-calculated from the storage modulus E' for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP using [8]

$$D_c(t) \sim 1/E(t) \quad (6)$$

$$E(t) \cong E'(\omega) \Big|_{\omega \rightarrow 2/\pi}$$

and approximate averaging method by Uemura [9]. The master curve of back-calculated D_c of matrix resin is shown in Fig.7. The master curve of D_c can be formulated by the following equation:

$$\log D_c = \log D_{c,0}(t'_0, T_0) + \log \left[\left(\frac{t'}{t'_0} \right)^{m_g} + \left(\frac{t'}{t'_g} \right)^{m_r} \right] \quad (7)$$

where $D_{c,0}$ is the creep compliance at reduced reference time t'_0 and reference temperature T_0 , and t'_g is the glassy reduced time on T_0 , and m_g and m_r

are the gradients in glassy and rubbery regions of D_c master curve. Parameters obtained from the formulations for $a_{T_0}(T)$, $b_{T_0}(T)$, and D_c are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 4. Master curve of loss tangent for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Fig. 5. Master curve of storage modulus for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Fig. 6. Shift factors of storage modulus for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Fig. 7. Master curves of creep compliance for matrix resin calculated from the storage modulus for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Table 1. Parameters for master curve and shift factors of creep compliance for matrix resin

T_0 [°C]	25	ΔH_1 [kJ/mol]	151
T_g [°C]	192	ΔH_2 [kJ/mol]	760
D_{c0} [1/GPa]	0.340	b_0	-3.10E-02
t_0^* [min]	1	b_1	1.84E-04
t_g^* [min]	6.28E10	b_2	-3.37E-05
m_g	0.0172	b_3	2.06E-07
m_t	0.442	b_4	-4.11E-10

5.2 Master curves of static and fatigue strengths for unidirectional CFRP

Figures 8 and 9 show the master curves of static and fatigue strengths for longitudinal tension X , longitudinal compression X' , transverse tension Y and transverse compression Y' for unidirectional CFRP which are constructed obtained from the strength data at various temperatures using the time-temperature shift factors a_{T_0} shown in Fig. 6. The solid and dotted curves in these figures show the fitting curves by Eq.(1) using the master curves of creep compliance of matrix resin in Fig. 7. The parameters obtained by formulation are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 8. Master curves of static strength for unidirectional CFRP

Fig. 9. Master curve of fatigue strength for unidirectional CFRP

Table 2. Parameters for master curve of static and fatigue strengths of unidirectional CFRP

	X	X'	Y	Y'
σ_{s0}	3048	2592	108	219
α_s	33.5	16.6	12.0	10.4
α_f	10.3	20.3	8.38	7.45
n_r	0.185	0.992	1.96	2.13
n_f	0.0497	0.0122	0.0427	0.0732
n_f^*	$n_f/2$	$n_f/2$	$n_f/2$	$n_f/2$
k_D	1	1	1	1

5.3 Master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters

The MMF/ATM critical parameter master curves T_f , C_f , T_m and C_m are shown in Fig. 10 determined from master curves of X , X' , Y , Y' and mechanical properties.

Fig. 10. Master curves of MMF/ATM critical parameters

5.4 Prediction of OHC strengths for QIL

As an example of application of MMF/ATM critical parameters master curves, the long-term OHC strength for QIL was predicted. Figure 11 shows the failure index distribution map for static test under 25°C. k_{Tf} and k_{Cf} are the failure index of fiber under tension and compression. k_{Tm} and k_{Cm} are the failure index of matrix under tension and compression. Numbers indicate the maximum value of failure index at the edge of hole in Fig. 11. When one of these failure indexes reaches to unity, the initial failure of laminate occurs.

Figures 12(a), (b), and (c) show the failure indexes of MMF/ATM parameters under static loading. It can be predicted that the OHC static failure under $T=25^\circ\text{C}$ and 80°C of QIL was triggered by fiber compressive failure in 0° layer. The OHC static failure under $T=150^\circ\text{C}$ of QIL was triggered by matrix compressive failure in $\pm 45^\circ$ layer. Figures 12(d), (e), and (f) shows the initial failure of OHC for QIL under static loading observed from the specimen in which the OHC test was stopped before final failure under various temperatures. For $T=25^\circ\text{C}$, and 80°C , the microbuckling of fiber in 0° layer is observed near the edge of hole. For $T=150^\circ\text{C}$, the transverse crack in 45° layer is observed near the edge of hole. These results agree well with predicted ones.

Figures 13 (a), (b), and (c) show the initial failure the failure indexes of MMF/ATM parameters under fatigue loading. It can be predicted that the OHC fatigue failure of QIL was triggered by matrix compressive failure in $\pm 45^\circ$ layer under all temperature tested. Figures 13(d), (e), and (f) shows the initial failure of OHC for QIL under fatigue loading observed from the specimen in which the OHC test was stopped before final failure. For fatigue test, the transverse crack in 45° layer is observed near the edge of hole under all temperature tested. These results agree well with predicted ones. Figure 14 shows the predicted master curves of static and fatigue OHC strengths for QIL with experimental data. The black and gray solid lines in the figure are predicted strengths for which the initial failure is compression of fiber in 0° layer and compression of matrix in $\pm 45^\circ$ layer. The predicted strength for which the initial failure is compression of fiber in 0° layer agrees well with the experimental data for all region of time to failure t' .

6 Conclusion

The static and fatigue strengths of quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates with a central hole under compression load as an example of CFRP structures were measured at elevated temperatures, and these experimental data agreed well with the predicted results based on MMF/ATM method.

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Fig. 11. Failure index distribution map under static OHC loading for QIL ($T=25^\circ\text{C}$, $V=0.1\text{mm/min}$, $\sigma=373\text{MPa}$)

Fig. 12. Prediction and observation of initial failure at the edge of hole of OHC for QIL under static loading

Fig. 13. Prediction and observation of initial failure at the edge of hole of OHC for QIL under fatigue loading

Fig. 14. Prediction of static and fatigue OHC strengths for QIL

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